

Effect of ZrO_2 substitution on the sintering behavior of cordierite ceramics

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Cordierite ceramics has been prepared with improved thermomechanical properties by the incorporation of ZrO_2 . An optimum amount of ZrO_2 (10%) was found to evolve the proper microstructure for obtaining the desirable properties.

Cordierite is rare as a natural mineral but the artificial products of this composition is of great importance because the coefficient of expansion is less than vitreous silica and they possess great thermal shock resistance. Moriya *et al.*¹ investigated the influence of Al_2O_3 and cordierite crystals on the formation of cordierite in $MgO-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ glass. Rew *et al.*² obtained cordierite ceramics with low electrical constants through sol-gel techniques using magnesium ethoxide, Al-isopropoxide and tetraethylorthosilicate as starting metal alkoxide. Ryu³ developed cordierite ceramics with low dielectric constant through sol-gel technique. Kondo⁴ studied the effect of calcined kaolin grain size on the firing process and physical properties of cordierite ceramics using kaolin, talc and $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ as starting materials. Sumi *et al.*⁵ investigated thermal reactions and sintering characteristics to obtain dense cordierite ceramics using kaolin. Lee⁶ prepared amorphous cordierite precursor powders by solution polymerization. Calata and Lu⁷ studied the densification behavior of cordierite glass ceramics films. Umehara⁸ discussed the production and properties of porous cordierite honeycomb catalyst support for vehicle exhaust emission. Camerucci *et al.*⁹ studied the cordierite ceramic by slip casting. Galakov¹⁰ studied the phase transformation or polymeric Al, Si, Mg gels of cordierite composition with addition of 5 wt% TiO_2 , ZrO_2 and CeO_2 . Nakahara *et al.*¹¹ studied the effect of impurity in starting kaolin materials on the sintering behavior of cordierite ceramics. Yue *et al.*¹² studied low temperature sinterable cordierite glass ceramics for high frequency multilayer chip inductor using a sol-gel process.

Present investigation was undertaken with the object of preparing cordierite bodies from indigenous raw materials along with zircon incorporation for enlargement of softening range and improvement of properties.

Results and Discussion

Tata batch composition (Table 1) was selected in such a manner that maximum amount of cordierite will be generated from clay-talc mixture for the improvement of the thermomechanical characteristics.

Table 1. Batch composition of the samples

Sample no.	Batch composition (%)		
	Talc	clay	Zircon
C1	70	30	—
C2	65	30	5
C3	60	30	10
C4	55	30	15

ZrO_2 was added in the form of zircon sand as a substitute for talc keeping the clay content same. The batch mixture was calcined at 900° . The consolidation was carried out using 15% uncalcined material as bond.

Fig. 1. Variation of firing shrinkage of the samples with firing temperature.

The firing shrinkage was related to the removal of residual water and particle interaction and coalescence. The shrinkage curves exhibited discontinuities (Fig. 1) and with the incorporation of ZrO_2 the inflection point became sharper. The break-point was identical, i.e. at 1250° , which was thought to be the temperature of cordierite formation. Shrinkage rate increased faster beyond 1250° , which might be associated with liquid formation.

The nature of the reaction sintering process during cordierite formation was characterized by measuring the change of apparent porosity with temperature (Fig. 2). The nature of the curve did not show any deviation with the incorporation of ZrO_2 . Porosity decreased with increase in temperature but not a continuous path indicating specific interaction in certain zone. Up to 1250° , the reduction of porosity was rather slow followed by sharp fall at 1300° .

Fig. 2. Variation of apparent porosity of the samples with firing temperature.

This clearly indicated the zone of cordierite formation along with some liquid formation. Thus the incorporation of ZrO_2 in this range did not expand the firing range of cordierite. With the increase of ZrO_2 content the porosity decreased due to the increased dissociation of zircon in presence of alkaline earth cations, i.e. Mg^{II} present in talc.

The mechanical strength of the body is very much related to the application of cordierite body. The MOR value was found to be a direct function of ZrO_2 content and it increased with firing temperature up to 1250° and then sharply decreased onwards. This might be due to decomposition of cordierite phase with increased glass formation.

The development of the different phases in the reaction sintered product is indicated by the change in the true density which are given in Table 2.

Density gradually decreased with firing temperature and the nature of the curves was identical in nature. In this case

also an inflection was noticed at 1250° . Density values were directly related to the amount of ZrO_2 . The inflection point in the curve indicated the optimum formation of the different phases. The downward trend of density change at elevated temperature appears to be due to enhanced glass formation.

Table 2. Variation of true density (g/ml) at firing temperatures ($^\circ C$)

Sample no.	1150°	1200°	1250°	1300°
C1	2.85	2.75	2.72	2.67
C2	2.90	2.78	2.77	2.71
C3	2.97	2.80	2.79	2.73
C4	3.00	2.87	2.84	2.78

Thermal shock resistance is very much related to the applications of cordierite ceramics. The experiment was conducted at 800° followed by a quenching and the cycle duration was 10 min etc. The residual flexural strength was determined after 8th cycle for each composition with increase of firing temperature. The strength increased almost in a linear path for all compositions, the slight deviation might be due to fabrication defects. That ZrO_2 contributed positively to the thermal shock resistance was evident from the values at 1250° . It is interesting to note that sufficient strength was retained after thermal cycling to be used in the adverse condition.

X-Ray analysis was performed to ascertain the crystalline phases developed in the fired bodies. The major phase identified was cordierite along with mullite and cordierite. Cubic zirconia was also observed, indicating complete stabilization of zirconia. Qualitatively, ZrO_2 bearing samples exhibited identical XRD pattern. The presence of trace amount of zirconia might be due to incompleteness of the dissociation of zircon. The phase transformation of ZrO_2 was assisted by MgO and the impurities associated with zircon.

The SEM micrographs of the samples were taken at 1250° at different compositions. The samples without ZrO_2 exhibited growth of cordierite crystals with sharp grain boundary. The distribution was more or less homogeneous. In some cases distribution of glassy phase was seen at the grain boundary. Grain boundary was sharper with the incorporation of ZrO_2 and the amount of glassy phase reduced. Both intra- and inter-granular ZrO_2 were observed. At the highest ZrO_2 concentration, the grain distribution was more oriented. The intragranular ZrO_2 was smaller than inter-granular ones.

Thus it may be concluded that ZrO_2 incorporation in cordierite matrix improve the thermomechanical properties

of the material. The zone of cordierite formation remained unaffected. In this particular set of compositions it was fired at 1250° for the formation of cordierite phase, and as such an inflection was observed in all the property-temperature relationships irrespective of compositions.

Experimental

For each batch, the required quantities of raw materials were weighed separately and taken in a porcelain pot for milling under wet condition using 80% water on the total weight of the batch. After milling for 2 h, the slip was evaporated to dryness. The dried mass was kneaded properly with 20% water whereby a semi-stiff plastic mass was obtained which was kept under humid condition for fabrication.

Rectangular bars (6.35 × 1.25 × 1.20 cm) were fabricated and dried at 110 ± 2° in an oven for 24 h. Firing was carried out at 1150, 1200, 1250 and 1300° in an electrically heated muffle furnace; up to 600°, the heating rate was 5°/min followed by 10°/min up to the final temperature of heat treatment. The soaking period was fixed at 30 min.

The fired samples were subjected to the usual tests. Except drying shrinkage, all the tests were done on fired

samples. The tests carried out were firing shrinkage, drying shrinkage, porosity, true density, mechanical strength, thermal shock resistance, XRD and scanning electron microscopy.

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